

Towards model-to-measurement data cubes with rigorous uncertainty propagation

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Abstract

Analytically intractable uncertainty structures occur across the Earth system sciences when large datasets from numerical simulations and measurements are compared. In paleoclimatology, proxy system models map Earth system model (ESM) output onto proxy measurements through a process chain with multiple sources of autocorrelated and non-Gaussian uncertainties. Here, we aim at integrating point measurements and Monte Carlo techniques for uncertainty quantification into a data cube architecture, with paleoclimate proxies as example. Our python package cupsm implements metadata rich objects for paleoclimate simulations and proxy data that permit lazy loading and parallelized data cube operations. Operators mapping between the two objects propagate uncertainties with Monte Carlo methods. A tutorial demonstrates our approach by comparing transient simulations from the Last Glacial Maximum to present-day with a database of sea surface temperature reconstructions from biological and geochemical proxies. cupsm improves interoperability and reusability of data analysis workflows in paleoclimatology. The package is available as open source repository and has been presented at the EGU2024 conference and within NFDI4Earth activities. cupsm has the potential to operationalize the evaluation of paleoclimate simulations from model intercomparison projects. It can also serve as a proof-of-concept for other Earth system science communities in which measurement operators are subject to complex uncertainties.

I. Introduction

Numerical models are a fundamental tool for understanding the Earth system. To test the reliability of models, they need to be compared with observational data. This task often involves operators that map model output onto the measurement space. In many Earth system science disciplines such as climatology (Kennedy et al., 2019), hydrology (McMillan et al., 2018), and remote sensing (Merchant et al., 2017), operators need to propagate complex uncertainty structures, which are analytically intractable. In paleoclimatology, so-called proxy system models (PSMs) map Earth system model (ESM) output onto proxy measurements from natural climate archives such as ice and sediment cores (Evans et al., 2013). PSMs consist of process chains with multiple sources of autocorrelated and non-Gaussian uncertainties (Dolman and Laepple, 2018).

Over time, the amounts of ESM data available for analysis has increased substantially, due to higher spatial resolutions, more complex representations of processes, inclusion of more compartments of the Earth system, longer simulation periods, and increased ensemble sizes to represent uncertainties from initial and boundary conditions and model limitation. Processing this model output creates a computational bottleneck. This fostered the development of efficient processing methods on data cubes for gridded ESM output such as ESMValTool (Eyring et al., 2020), MetPy (May et al., 2022), and xCDAT (Vo et al., 2024). Many of these packages are written in python, which has emerged as the leading programming language for processing and analyzing ESM output. Most data cube implementations in python are compatible with NetCDF files for raster data, which is the standard data format for ESM output.

Meanwhile, paleoclimate proxy data is mostly stored in a variety of tabular and database formats. This is because the collection of paleoclimate proxies is an interdisciplinary process with different communities following different data management and metadata reporting conventions. For example, proxy collections compiled in recent years tend to use different data formats (e.g., Herzsuh et al., 2022, Jonkers et al., 2020a, Kaushal et al., 2024, Sánchez Goñi et al., 2017). A suite of processing tools for proxy data exists, for example to infer age-depth relationships (e.g., Blaauw and Christen, 2011), reconstruct environmental conditions (e.g., Tierney and Tingley, 2018), or model non-climatic processes that modulate the climate signal recorded by the proxy (e.g., Dolman and Laepple, 2018). These tools are usually not designed to perform computations efficiently on large datasets because the size of individual proxy record datasets is comparatively small. However, uncertainties of paleoclimate proxies tend to be non-Gaussian and autocorrelated, which makes them analytically intractable. Therefore, Monte Carlo methods are convenient for rigorous uncertainty quantification. Together with more comprehensive proxy record databases, this creates a need for incorporating big data methods into the evaluation of ESMs against paleoclimate proxies. This evaluation is valuable not just to

understand past climate but also to improve future Earth system projections because past climate states provide an out-of-sample test for ESMs.

To leverage the progress in ESMs, global proxy databases, and PSMs for climate process understanding and model validation, efficient processing of ESM output needs to be combined with Monte Carlo methods for uncertainty propagation, and point measurements such as paleoclimate proxies need to be incorporated into climate data cubes. This pilot addressed these challenges by

1. developing flexible data objects in python for collections of paleoclimate proxy data and transient climate simulations that make use of data cube concepts;
2. implementing operators that map ESM output onto proxy measurements with a rigorous propagation of uncertainties through Monte Carlo methods;
3. creating example workflows that compare the simulated sea surface temperature (SST) evolution over the last 20,000 years with SST proxies from geochemical and biological proxies.

The pilot contributes to more efficient, interoperable, and reusable model-proxy comparison workflows that combine all mappings between ESM output and proxy measurements. Our prototype lays the groundwork for tackling new research questions in paleoclimatology such as evaluating the ability of ESMs to simulate climate variability patterns across spatial and temporal scales. Furthermore, the concepts developed in this pilot can be applied to measurement operators with complex uncertainty structures in other Earth system science disciplines.

II. Results

a) Concepts

Data cubes are an increasingly popular paradigm for efficiently processing and visualizing large raster datasets in the Earth system sciences (Mahecha et al., 2020). Data cubes are designed to efficiently perform operations that require only small chunks of large datasets, by parallelizing computations and loading only chunks of datasets which are needed for a specific operation, so called lazy loading. These are in particular operations that only require data along a subset of the dimensions of a dataset. This is the case in most paleoclimate applications that operate along either the temporal or the spatial dimension. Uncertainty quantification with Monte Carlo or Markov Chain Monte Carlo methods are suitable for data cube architectures because samples are (approximately) independent. This makes operations embarrassingly parallel, i.e., they can be performed without communication between samples. Exploiting embarrassingly parallel operations and lazy loading facilitates efficient memory and cpu usage.

Proxy system models (PSMs) are mathematical models that map between gridded model output and point data from paleoclimate proxies by imitating processes that the measured proxy has been subjected to. This includes:

- Restricting climate signals to the spatial area recorded by a proxy;
- Computing auxiliary variables recorded by the proxy which are not directly simulated by ESMs;
- Simulating archival processes that modify the recorded climate signal such as bioturbation for marine sediment cores;
- Resampling to the temporally integrated and irregularly spaced time axis of a proxy record, which itself is determined by statistically inferring ages of samples from their depth in a record;
- Applying statistical calibrations between measured quantities and climate variables.

Existing PSM functionalities are usually implemented in only one of the available scripting languages, including python (e.g., Khider et al., 2022), R (e.g., Dolman and Lapple, 2018), and matlab (e.g., Tierney and Tingley, 2018), and written with the goal of imitating only one proxy record at a time. This hampers their use in computationally efficient analysis workflows to date.

Applying a PSM to ESM output results in an ensemble of forward-modeled proxy time series if uncertainties in the simulations and PSM are quantified with Monte Carlo methods. Therefore, quantitative comparisons of forward-modeled proxy time series and measured proxies require computing the deviations between probability distributions. So-called strictly proper score or divergence functions are particularly well suited for this task because their mathematical properties reward honest assessments of uncertainties (Gneiting and Raftery, 2007, Thorarinsdottir et al., 2013). Examples previously employed in (paleo)climatology are Brier scores (Weitzel et al., 2019), the continuous ranked probability score (Werner et al., 2018), and the integrated quadratic distance (Weitzel et al., 2024a). Integrating these metrics is the final step of model-proxy comparison workflows (Fig. 1, Weitzel et al., 2024a).

We implement our pilot in python due to its widespread use for analyzing ESM output with data cube architectures and available tools for uncertainty quantification with Monte Carlo methods (e.g., Kumar et al., 2019). Among the existing data cube implementations in python, we select xarray (Hoyer and Hamman, 2017) as a flexible architecture, which is compatible with packages for processing ESM output (e.g., May et al., 2022, Vo et al., 2024) and postprocessing and visualizing Monte Carlo based inferences (e.g., ARVIZ, Kumar et al., 2019). Furthermore, it is interoperable with other data cube implementations such as iris data cubes (Iris contributors, 2024).

Fig. 1: Conceptual workflow for model-proxy comparison in paleoclimatology. Starting from ESM output (top left) forward-modeled proxy time series (bottom left) are constructed by applying a chain of operators which together build a PSM. The forward-modeled proxy time series are compared with reconstructed climate time series (bottom right) which are inferred from proxies measured in natural climate archives (top right). The probability distributions formed by forward-modeled proxy time series and reconstructions are compared using strictly proper score or divergence functions. Sources of graphics: climatearchive.org, Kira Rehfeld (pers. comm.), Weitzel et al., 2024a.

b) Data objects

Two base objects are needed for model-proxy comparison, one for ESM output (*sim_data*) and one for proxy data (*obs_data*). The *obs_data* object is also used to store forward-model proxy time series, which have the same structure as proxy data. PSM operators are mapping between *sim_data* and *obs_data* objects (or intermediate products in the case of sequential application of operators). The structure of the two objects is depicted in Fig. 2.

We load simulation data as an `xarray.Dataset` which has coordinates *time*, *lon*, *lat*, *level* (vertical dimension), and optionally *ens* (ensemble members). Each ESM variable is loaded as an `xarray.DataArray` within the `xarray.Dataset`. Using a standard `xarray` object structure has the advantage that existing ESM processing functionalities can be applied in addition to PSM operators. The `xarray.Dataset` structure facilitates lazy loading and parallelization of operations by chunking datasets, which is of importance for the large data size of long paleoclimate simulations (see Sect. 2d).

In collections of proxy records, the number of samples and the measured and reconstructed variables tend to differ between measurement sites (here *site* refers to a specific location where a proxy archive is collected; archives can for example be sediment or ice cores). We use an `xarray.Dataset` for data from a single site (*site_object*), which has the dimensions *depth* or *age* (samples are identified by depth in a sediment core or by their inferred ages) and *ens* (ensemble members to quantify uncertainties), and can store four types of variables: chronological data, measured proxy data, inferred variables such as temperature reconstructions, and forward-modeled proxy time series derived from applying a PSM to ESM output. The *site_objects* contain relevant metadata as attributes. Our *obs_data* object is a dictionary or list of *site_objects*. We do not use a data cube architecture on the top level of the *obs_data* object because of the strong heterogeneity of the *site_objects*. The dictionary/list structure allows loading of the *site_object* data based on metadata filtering, by first creating an overview table containing only the site metadata before loading the site data into memory in a second step. We demonstrate parallelization over *site_objects* with the python library `dask`². Within one *site_object*, operations can also be parallelized using existing `xarray` functionalities.

For the naming conventions of our objects and metadata, we build on the LinkedEarth ontology (Emile-Geay et al., 2019) for paleoclimate data and the `xarray` standards.

c) Proxy system model operators

For our prototype, we implemented three types of operators: space operators (*field2site*) that map the spatial fields of the *sim_data* onto the spatial structure of the *site_objects*, chronology operators (*time2chron*) that map data from the regular *sim_data* time axis onto the irregular *site_object* time axis, and exemplifying variable operators that perturb the data in *sim_data* or

²<https://www.dask.org>

Fig. 2: Measurement operators translate the *sim_data* (top, given by a chunked xarray DataArray for the variable 'tos', which is the CMOR variable name of SST, with space and time dimensions) into an *obs_data* object (bottom), which is given by N site_objects. Each site_object contains an xarray Dataset with dimensions depth, where K_1, \dots, K_N are the number of samples at the respective sites, and *ens*, where L is the number of ensemble members.

site_objects with either white or autocorrelated noise to imitate uncertainties from the proxy-climate relationship and archival processes. Using these three types of operations follows the PSM in Weitzel et al. (2024a) for comparing simulated and reconstructed SSTs for the last deglaciation, i.e., the transition from the Last Glacial Maximum (~21,000 years before present) to the current warm period, the Holocene.

For each operator type, we tested different parallelization strategies. The space operator reduces the required memory for loading full data objects the most. Therefore, the most efficient way here was to recombine internal xarray functions that make use of lazy loading such that the *sim_data* object never needs to be loaded completely into memory. The

chronology operator takes the output of the space operator, but using the inherited chunk structure is very inefficient. Instead a combination of using vectorized xarray functions within a *site_object* and parallelizing over all *site_objects* with *dask* is the most efficient strategy. Therefore, these two operators need to be executed sequentially as otherwise the *dask* task graph would grow too large for an efficient execution.

d) Examples

To demonstrate our approach, we make use of a transient simulation of the last 26,000 years with the MPI-ESM model (Kapsch et al., 2022) and a collection of proxy records from marine sediment cores, the “PALMOD 130k marine palaeoclimate data synthesis V1_0_1” (Jonkers et al., 2020a). We compare simulated and reconstructed SSTs from these datasets. The MPI-ESM output is provided as NetCDF files, with each file containing data for 100 simulation years and metadata and variable names follow the CMOR standard for climate model output. The “PALMOD 130k marine palaeoclimate data synthesis V1_0_1” is provided as a collection of files in the LiPD format (McKay and Emile-Geay, 2016), a metadata rich file format for paleoclimate data adopting the LinkedEarth ontology.

The total size of the MPI-ESM SST output is ~8GB on an unstructured grid. Since the space operator requires data on a regular lat-lon grid as input, we include a regridding step of the SST data in our tutorial, prior to applying the PSM operators. For the regridding, we use the xarray-based python package *xESMF*. After regridding, the size of the *sim_data* object is ~11GB which makes lazy loading strongly preferential. Loading the SST reconstructions requires extensive automated quality control to avoid samples having the same depth, incorrect sorting of data, and other data inconsistencies. The *obs_data* object is created in a two step approach. First, all LiPD files are loaded to construct an overview table containing only the metadata. This table is stored locally and used in subsequent sessions to read in *site_objects* based on metadata filters to avoid having to load all *site_objects* in every session.

We demonstrate the use of the operators through tutorials that apply them sequentially, showing the impact that the individual steps have on the resulting forward-modeled proxy time series (Fig. 3). To model uncertainties related to the age-depth relationship, we make use of an ensemble of age-depth relationships constructed with the Bayesian age modeling software BACON (Blaauw and Christen, 2011), which is included in the LiPD files of the “PALMOD 130k marine palaeoclimate data synthesis V1_0_1”.

The tutorials are provided as jupyter notebooks, together with a *yaml* file to recreate the python environment used for the package development. Visualizations of the results are included in the notebooks.

Fig. 3: Example of a 26,000 years long transient simulation of the last deglaciation with MPI-ESM (gray) and reconstructed SST anomalies from proxies archived in five marine sediment cores (green, see map for locations). A habitat season is selected (color-coded dots on the map) and the simulation is downsampled to the proxy time axes, with quantification of chronological uncertainties (blue).

e) Data and Software availability

Our software development is wrapped in the python package *cupsm*, which can be downloaded and installed from github (<https://github.com/paleovar/cupsm>). The release version (v1.0.0) is archived on zenodo (Weitzel et al., 2025). Future development of the package is envisaged (see Sect. 5) and subsequent release versions will also be archived on zenodo. *cupsm* is published under a MIT License. The release version contains the source code described in Sect. 2b and Sect. 2c, and tutorials showing the examples from Sect. 2d. The concepts, objects, and functions are documented on readthedocs (<https://cupsm.readthedocs.io>). The current package structure is visualized in Fig. 4.

The data used in the tutorials is published under CC-BY-4.0 licenses and can be downloaded using bash scripts provided in the data directory of the repository. The proxy data is published on Pangaea (Jonkers et al., 2020b). The link to the LiPD version of the database is https://store.pangaea.de/Publications/Jonkers-etal_2019/V1_0_1/LiPD.zip. The simulation output is published on the Palmod ESGF (Mikolajewicz et al., 2023) which can be accessed via

Fig. 4: Structure of the python package *cupsm*, that contains the objects and operators implemented in this pilot.

<https://cmiphub.cloud.dkrz.de/esgf-projects/palmod.php> or <https://esgf-metagrid.cloud.dkrz.de/search>. Downloading requires the creation of an ESGF account. To make the tutorials a realistic use case, we decided to use a real-world application with large datasets instead of a small toy example. This requires not directly including the datasets in the package but provide download instructions instead.

f) Innovation and FAIRness

Our python package *cupsm* provides two innovations compared to the status quo. First, it provides a data structure for point measurements, specifically irregularly spaced and uncertain time series data, that is suitable for integrating point measurements into data cube concepts. Second, it provides a prototype for model-data comparison workflows in the presence of measurement operators subject to complex uncertainty structures.

Our pilot is a step towards more efficient, interoperable, and reusable model-proxy comparison workflows that combine all mappings between ESM output and paleoclimate proxy measurements. The modular approach of the package allows further integration of existing PSM functionalities and datasets in the future. The open source publication of *cupsm* facilitates the dissemination of our results, further development of the prototype, and future contributions by external collaborators.

III. Challenges and Gaps

Two of the planned tasks could not be implemented due to time limitations. These are (1) testing the efficiency of integrating existing PSM functionalities in R through a parallelized python wrapper, and (2) implementing metrics for measuring the deviation between forward-model proxy time series and paleoclimate proxies. The latter was conceptually demonstrated in

a paper, which was published during the project duration (Weitzel et al. 2024a), but is not yet integrated into *cupsm*.

The main reason for not implementing these two functionalities have been two challenges that were more time-consuming than planned. First, even though the lead PI of the pilot had prior experience with all datasets used in our tutorials, reading, cleaning, and processing the SST proxy database involved more individual time than expected. This was partly because the LiPD utilities for python (Heiser et al., 2018) only allowed to either store the site data in a multiple nested object or extract just a small subset of the data/metadata. Second, implementing operators that efficiently parallelize tasks with dask was more challenging than expected. In particular, mixing existing xarray functionalities that employ dask with functions that are parallelized with dask by hand was in most cases not efficient because it created task graphs that were too complex to be executed efficiently.

The challenges of rewriting operators using dask are not a problem unique to our pilot (see, e.g., the report from a natESM sprint to rewrite preprocessor functions of the ESM evaluation toolbox ESMValTool³) and it is easier to reach a high memory and cpu efficiency when functions are directly designed for parallelization. This asks the question to what extend efforts should be put into writing wrappers to parallelize existing functions compared to reimplementing functionalities in a scalable design. Automatic code rewriting tools could be an option in the future for both approaches and at this point, we cannot give a general recommendation on the preferable solution.

In either case, we recommend the treatment of legacy code and its integration into modern architectures like data cubes to be a focus of future discussions in NFDI4Earth and domain-specific communities. This is of particular interest in communities which are highly interdisciplinary and have in the past relied on unstructured code developments instead of projects in which large code bases have been created with a high level of gate keeping and governance.

Similarly, the challenge of heterogeneous observational datasets is not specific to this pilot but has been addressed for example in other NFDI4Earth pilot projects (e.g., *Reusability of Data with Complex Semantic Structure*, *OcMOD: Observations closer to Model Data*, *NFDI for Seamless Earth System Model-Data Integration*, *Linking Environmental Data into European Scale Research Infrastructures*, *Developing Tools and FAIR Principles for the MetBase Database*, *BPMN4Earth*). Especially for the compilation of new databases, the suitability for computationally efficient processing should be an important criterion in the decision for a data format. Within NFDI4Earth, discussions can go beyond community-specific solutions and develop overarching

³https://www.nat-esm.de/services/support-through-sprints/accepted-sprints/20240513-natesm_sprint_docu_esmvaltool_final.pdf

strategies for making optimal use of heterogeneous archives of observational datasets such as PANGAEA⁴.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

Preliminary results from this pilot have been presented at EGU2024 (Weitzel et al., 2024b) and within the NFDI4Earth community (during the NFDI4Earth plenum 2024 and within the NFDI4Earth academy). The feedback gathered during these presentations has fed back into the software development. The software development is connected to national and international activities that the PIs Nils Weitzel and Kira Rehfeld are involved in, in particular PalMod⁵, PMIP (Paleoclimate Model Intercomparison Project)⁶, natESM⁷, and PAGES CVAS (Climate Variability across Scales)⁸.

It is envisaged to promote *cupsm* in the context of PMIP and PAGES CVAS as a tool for evaluating and tuning ESMs against paleoclimate proxies. To achieve this goal, further developments towards operational evaluation workflows with *cupsm* are needed (see Sect. 5). Using *cupsm* for the benchmarking of paleoclimate simulations would close a gap in the evaluation of ESMs which has been standardized in recent years for simulations of the instrumental period through projects such as PCMDI (Lee et al., 2024) and ESMValTool (Eyring et al., 2020).

The main user group of *cupsm* are (paleo)climatologists, in particular Earth system modelers and paleoclimate proxy experts. *cupsm* is especially suited to explore research questions which require the use of long simulations with comprehensive ESMs, large proxy data compilations, and rigorous uncertainty quantification. Using harmonized data structures for paleoclimate simulations and proxies in *cupsm* makes ESM output and proxy data more accessible, in particular to users who are not working with the respective data types regularly. This can foster new collaborations between proxy experts and climate modelers.

Furthermore, scientists from the wider NFDI4Earth community and other Earth system science disciplines, in which uncertainty quantification for large datasets are important, could integrate our concepts into their workflows. Our vision also emphasizes the benefit of using file formats in data repositories that are compatible with big data concepts, even if the individual datasets are comparatively small.

⁴<https://www.pangaea.de/>

⁵palmod.de

⁶pmip4.lsce.ipsl.fr

⁷nat-esm.de

⁸<https://pastglobalchanges.org/science/wg/cvas/intro>

V. Future Directions

Future work and recommended directions towards model-to-measurement data cubes with rigorous uncertainty propagation can be divided into three aspects: short-term plans, mid-term goals, and long-term visions.

In the short-term, further development and maintenance of *cupsm* is ensured through project funding of Nils Weitzel and in-kind contributions of Nils Weitzel and Kira Rehfeld to national and international projects. The focus is on two applications: evaluation of paleoclimate simulations and ESM tuning. Enhancing the functionalities for evaluating paleoclimate simulations is planned with a focus on long simulations and multi-model ensembles from the PMIP and PalMod projects. For temporally autocorrelated uncertainties, these are in particular transient simulations of the last deglaciation, the Holocene, and the Common Era. Furthermore, evaluation capabilities for time slice simulations of the Last Glacial Maximum, mid-Holocene, mid-Pliocene warm period, and the last interglacial can be enhanced with *cupsm* by better representing spatially autocorrelated uncertainties. The extension of the available operators and integrated datasets, and the implementation of probabilistic divergence functions can facilitate the development of a 'cookbook' for evaluating paleoclimate simulations, exploiting the modular approach of *cupsm*.

The future work on *cupsm* will be coordinated by PI1 Nils Weitzel as part of his Marie Curie Research Fellow project PALVEGMOD, which started in November 2024. The goal of this project is to optimize the response of vegetation to carbon dioxide variations in a computationally efficient ESM by comparing ESM output against reconstructions of paleovegetation. Finding parameter combinations in ESMs, that are consistent with paleoclimate proxies, requires computationally efficient comparison methods to run optimization algorithms. Using *cupsm* for ESM tuning contributes also to the goals of the PAGES CVAS working group, in which Kira Rehfeld and Nils Weitzel are steering group members. PAGES CVAS aims particularly at improving the representation of decadal-to-millennial scale variability in ESMs. *cupsm* can also be used in other projects aiming at objectively tuning ESMs against paleoclimate proxies (e.g., Racky et al., 2024).

The mid-term goal is establishing complete model-to-measurement data cube workflows with rigorous uncertainty propagation in (paleo)climatology. This means that starting from an ensemble of simulations, in which ensemble members quantify uncertainties related to initial conditions, boundary conditions, and/or model limitations, a chain of process-based operators is applied to construct ensembles of forward-modeled proxy time series, which are then compared to uncertain measurements. It is envisaged to integrate these *cupsm* functionalities into an existing ESM evaluation tool for simulations of the instrumental period.

To avoid the necessity to download large amounts of data prior to applying *cupsm*, running it on a cloud-based high-performance computing infrastructure, where ESM output and collections of paleoclimate proxies and other observational datasets are stored, would be desirable. To achieve this, community solutions would be needed to bring together archiving systems for ESM output and observational datasets.

In the long-term, the vision of model-to-measurement data cubes with rigorous uncertainty propagation could be adopted by other Earth system science disciplines. This is possible since the concepts of this pilot can be applied to all measurement operators involving analytically intractable uncertainty structures. One obstacle at the moment is the distribution of measurement operator tools across programming languages (in particular python, R, Matlab, and Julia). The development of multi-language analysis platforms, which can take input syntax in any of these languages or pseudo-code, would be a barrier-breaking long-term development to achieve FAIR model-data comparison workflows. This work can build on promising prototypes like Earth System Data Lab (Mahecha et al. 2020). In connection with communication tools like large language models, this could also open up new opportunities to compare models and data for scientists working mainly in the field or lab that do not have the coding skills to run existing PSM modeling software. In addition, it could enhance visualization capacities for outreach activities.

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